

RAWE 2022-23

A COMPREHENSIVE REPORT ON RAWE PROGRAMME

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With Regards:

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INTRODUCTION

“If Agriculture fails, everything else will fail”

M.S. Swaminathan

WHAT IS RAWE

Rural Agricultural Work Experience (RAWE) program gives us the opportunity to understand the rural life and to work and interact with them. Study of Human behavior is the main focus of the program. It is necessary to motivate the farmers to adapt to new methods of cultivation to improve their standards and mode of life. The overall objective of RAWE program is to bring possible development of rural people. It is achieved by means of bringing desirable changes among the rural communities. Since, adoption of new idea is a complex process, awareness, interest, trials and adoption of new ideas among the farming communities should be carried out effectively and systematically. Adoption is also influenced by age, sex, and level of education of the farmers. The youths of today are the citizens of tomorrow. The progress and prosperity of a state and country depends to a large extent on the training and discipline of the youths. Social change is one of the most significant phenomena occurring in rural societies all over the world, and one of the ways to bring a desirable social change is the RAWE program.

The Rural Agricultural Work Experience (RAWE) is a compulsory course offered in Vital Semester to B. Sc. (Hons.) Agriculture students primarily to understand the rural situations, status of Agricultural technologies adopted by farmers, prioritize the farmers problems and to develop skills & attitude of working with farm families for all-round development in rural area. The Rural Agricultural Work Experience (RAWE) provides exposure to agricultural students to the natural setting of the village situations, work with the farm families, identify their problems and make use of various extension tools for transferring the latest agricultural technologies. The students also get opportunity to study the various on-going schemes related to agriculture and rural development and participate in their implementation.

OBJECTIVES OF THE PROGRAMME

- To provide an opportunity to the students to understand the rural setting in relation to agriculture and allied activities.
- To get the students familiar with socio-economic conditions of the farmers and their problems with reference to agricultural development.
- To impart diagnostic and remedial knowledge to the students relevant to real field situations through practical training.
- To develop communication skills in students using extension teaching methods in transfer of technology.
- To develop confidence and competence to solve agricultural problems.
- To help students to acquaint with on-going extension and rural development programs.

METHODOLOGY

Household survey was conducted by the students of Palli siksha Bhavana, Visva Bharati under the course RAW (village attachment). The survey was done by following ‘Simple Random Sampling Without Replacement’ method. Each student interviewed individual farmer through a detailed questionnaire. The collected data are used for the educational purpose for calculating different costs and profit.

PASCHIM BAHADURPUR - VILLAGE OVERVIEW

INTRODUCTION

A detailed survey on village Bahadurpur was conducted by the students of Palli siksha Bhavana, Visva Bharati under the course RAW. The survey was done by following ‘Simple Random Sampling Without Replacement’ method. Each student interviewed 5 individual farmers through a detailed questionnaire. The collected data are used for the educational purpose and for understanding the different Cropping pattern, Livestock status, Soil nutrient status, Horticultural status, disease-pest infestation and socio-economic status of the village Bahadurpur.

Map of Bahadurpur
Source: Google Map

POPULATION OF PASCHIM BAHADURPUR

PARTICULARS	TOTAL	MALE	FEMALE
Total Population	753	385	368
Literate Population	493	271	222
Illiterate Population	260	114	146

Census Parameter	Census Data
Total Population	753
Total No of Houses	170
Female Population %	48.9 % (368)
Total Literacy rate %	65.5 % (493)
Female Literacy rate	29.5 % (222)
Scheduled Tribes Population %	0.4 % (3)
Scheduled Caste Population %	54.3 % (409)
Working Population %	35.6 %
Child(0 -6) Population by 2011	68
Girl Child(0 -6) Population % by 2011	51.5 % (35)

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT VILLAGE

Gram Panchayat	Ruppur
Block / Subdivision	Bolpur Sriniketan
District	Birbhum
State	West Bengal
Pin code	731236
Area	207.13 hectares
Total Population	753
Total Households	170
Assembly Constituency	Bolpur
Parliament Constituency	Bolpur
Nearest Town	Bolpur (9 km)
Distance Nearest Market	5 kms
Primary/Middle School	Bahadurpur Primary School, Binuria High School
High School/ Higher Secondary/College	Bengal Institute Of Technology And Management,doranda, Shantiniketan
Post Office	5 km
Railway Station	Bolpur Sriniketan railways
Bus Stand	0 km
Krishi Upaj Mandi	5 km (Sriniketan)
Transport facilities	Bus, Toto , Van , Mini truck etc
Nearest village	Binuria

Location and Administration: Paschim Bahadurpur Total area is 164 hectares, Forest area is 4 hectares, Non-Agricultural area is 35.1 hectares, Total irrigated area is 164 hectares and Total Water fall area is 0 hectares

Education: Government Pre Primary and Govt Primary Schools are available in this Village. Nearest Govt Secondary School and Govt Senior Secondary School are in **Binuria**. Nearest Govt Pre Primary School is in **Ruppur**. Nearest Private Engineering College is in **Santiniketan (BITM)**. Nearest Govt Arts and Science Degree College is in **Santiniketan**.

Agriculture: Rice is main agriculture crop grow in this village. Total irrigated area in this village is 164 hectares from canals 98 hectares, from Boreholes/Tube wells 49 hectares and from Lakes or tanks 17 hectares are the Sources of irrigation.

Drinking-Water and Sanitation: Treated Tap Water Supply all-round the year and in summer also available. Untreated Tap Water Supply all-round the year and in summer available. Tube Wells/Boreholes is other Drinking Water sources. Open Drainage System Available in this Village. There is no system to collect garbage on street. Drain water is discharged into sewer plant.

Communication: Landline available. Mobile Coverage is available. Nearest Internet Centre is in 5 - 10 km. No Private Courier Facility in less than 10 km.

Transportation: There is no Public Bus service in less than 10 km. There is no Railway Station in less than 10 km. Man pulled Cycle Rickshaws Available in this Village. Animal Driven Carts are there in this Village. Pucca road¹, Kuccha Road ²and Foot Path are other Roads and Transportation within the village.

Commerce: No ATM in less than 10 km. No Commercial Bank in less than 10 km. No Cooperative Bank in less than 10 km

INVOLVING IN FARM ACTIVITIES

- Involvement in day-to-day agricultural operation with host farmer,
- Calendar of operation for semester will be prepared in consultation with host farmer for a year, at least 2 crops, field and horticultural may be chosen,
- Comparison of farmers activities with the recommended practices,
- Choosing suitable recommended practice benefiting to farmer's situation & resources,
- Maintaining daily diary by students with abstract of work done,
- Review of daily diary by chairman and programme coordinator Survey and farm planning
- Make survey of the village, preparation of report and presentation.
- Collection of data on socio-economic condition, population, cropping pattern, irrigation facilities resources available, labour, employment.
- Identify the constraints in marketing of agricultural produce, institutional credit facilities, input supply agencies and cooperative enterprises.

¹ Bituminous Roads

² Earthen Roads

WORK DONE DURING RAWE 2022-23

Activities

1. General orientation & on campus training by different faculties.
2. Village attachment & KVK Attachment.
3. Agro-Industrial Attachment.
4. Project Report Preparation, Presentation and Evaluation

The RAWE programme consists of three parts

RAWE component I: consists of village attachment training programme which in turn consists of various interventions:

- Orientation and Survey of Village,
- Agronomical Interventions,
- Plant Protection Interventions,
- Soil Improvement Interventions (Soil sampling and testing),
- Fruit and Vegetable production interventions,
- Food Processing and Storage interventions,
- Animal Production Interventions,
- Extension and Transfer of Technology activities

We have performed each of these interventions and studied them through various aspects. Data with respect to each of these interventions are recorded and analysed in a systematic manner.

RAWE Component II: there is Agro Industrial Attachment under which students shall be placed in Agro-industries.

RAWE component III: consists of KVK attachment training programme.

RAWE VILLAGE ATTACHMENT

We have started our village attachment programme on 25th August 2022. On this programme of RAWE conducted by our college we were allotted to the village Bahadurpur, under Bolpur Sriniketan block. We went to the village and performed various activities according to the proforma given by our respected professors. We a group of 13 students went to the village in a systematic way and collected the data by interviewing the farmers.

**SCHEDULE OF RURAL AGRICULTURAL WORK EXPERIENCE AND
AGRO INDUSTRIAL ATTACHMENT (RAWE & AIA) w.e.f. 04TH
AUGUST, 2022**

Sl No.	Time Schedule	Component Description	Lead Faculty
1	04th August - 17th August, 2022 (2 Weeks)	KVK/Research Station Attachment	Dr. Anindita Saha (Dept. of Agril. Extension) Dr. S. Mandal RKVK
2	18th August -24th August, 2022 (01 Week)	Orientation Classes	HoDs and Departmental Representatives
3	25th August -31st August, 2022 (01 Week)	Soil Improvement Interventions	Dr. Pabitra K. Biswas (Dept. of Soil Sc. & Agril. Chem.)
4	01st September -07th September, 2022 (01 Week)	Food Processing and Mechanization Intervention	Dr.(Ms.)L. Hamshing (Dept. of Agril. Engineering)
5	8th September - 14th September, 2022 (01 Week)	Animal Production Intervention	Dr. Jayanta K. Chatterjee (Dept. of Animal Science)
6	15th September - 21st September, 2022 (01 Week)	Extension and Transfer of Technology	Dr. Darshan N. P. (Dept. of Agril. Extension)
7	22nd September - 19th October, 2022 (04 Weeks)	Agro-Industrial Attachment	Prof. D. Sarkar (Dept. of Agril Economics)
8	20th October - 26th October, 2022 (01 Week)	KVK/Research Station Attachment	Dr. Anindita Saha (Dept. of Agril. Extension) Dr. S. Mandal RKVK
9	27th October - 02nd November, 2022 (01 Week)	Survey of Villages	Mr. S. Gorain (Dept. of Agril Economics)
10	03rd-09th November, 2022 (01 Week)	Agronomical Intervention	Dr. P. Ghosh (Dept. of Agronomy)
11	10th November - 16th November, 2022 (05 Weeks)	Fruit and Vegetable Production	Dr. Prahlad Deb (Dept. of Horticulture & Post-Harvest Tech.)
12	17th November-23rd November, 2022 (1 week)	Plant Protection Intervention	Dr. Bholanath Mondal And Dr.(Ms.) S. Bhattacharya (Dept. of Plant Pathology & Agricultural Entomology)
13	24th November – 7 th December, 2022 (2 weeks)	KVK/Research Station Attachment	Dr. Anindita Saha (Dept. of Agril. Extension) Dr. S. Mandal RKVK

SOURCE OF LIVELIHOOD

During our village attachment week, we interacted with different villagers and got to know that the primary income source of the villagers is Farming³. Besides some other occupations are - Shop owner, Toto driver, Panipuriwala⁴, Vendor etc. Some of them also do Services.

MAJOR CROPPING SYSTEM FOLLOWED IN THE VILLAGE

- 1) Paddy-Potato- Brinjal (canal water)
- 2) Paddy-Potato-Fallow (Sallow water canal water)
- 3) Paddy-Mustard-Fallow (Pond, canal water)
- 4) Paddy-Wheat-Fallow (Submersible)
- 5) Paddy-Okra/Chili/Cucumber-Fallow (Pond, Canal water)

Figure 4 Brinjal and Cucumber Field

Figure 3 Rice Field

Figure 2 Ridge Gourd

Figure 1 Okra

³ Because of lack of capital and higher education they relied on agriculture sector

⁴ Water Pancakes or Water Balls

GENERAL CULTIVATION PRACTICES OF BAHADURPUR VILLAGE WITH EMPHASIS ON PADDY

DESCRIPTION OF EXISTING CROPS IN THE FIELDS OF BAHADURPUR VILLAGE: -

In Bahadurpur village, farmers mainly cultivate the paddy in Kharif season no in Summer⁵ season. There are a few major reasons behind the cultivation of Kharif rice. The reasons are: -

- The irrigation facilities are not so good in Bahadurpur village, that's why boro rice is not cultivated.
- Paddy is the main staple food of West Bengal. So, there is demand in the market and has good marketing chain available to the farmers.
- Cultivation of other crops are troublesome but in rice cultivation there is not that much headache and there is very lesser chance of 100% crop failure.

Season	Kharif	Rabi	Summer
Crop	Rice, Brinjal, Chili	Mustard, Potato	Cucumber, Pumpkin, Okra
Variety	Rice- MTU-7029, MTU-1010, Gotra selection, Miniket Brinjal- PusaShymala, Pusa Purple, Badkulla Chili- Not Known	Mustard- B-9, B-54 Potato- Jyoti	Cucumber – Not Known Pumpkin - Not Known Okra- Not Known

The farmers are using MTU-7029, MTU-1010, Gotra selection, Miniket variety of paddy. Most of seed sources are own farm-saved seeds⁶ and local seed shops. Cost of seed- Cost depends on variety. On an average generally 50-60kg/bag.

Seed rate = 50-60kg/ha. This rice is grown for **110-120 day**. Crop duration (Brinjal-5-month, Chili- 6-month, Mustard- 3-month, Potato- 3-4 month.)

Figure 7 Minikit

Figure 5 Gotra Selection

Figure 6 Swarna

⁵ Due to lack of irrigation facilities the villages didn't go for Summer season cultivation of Paddy. They general cultivate solanaceous crops.

⁶ Own farm seed that is cultivated previous year and store the seeds, although they didn't get promising yield using these seeds so they purchased seeds from local shop.

Figure 10 Chili

Figure 8 Brinjal

Figure 9 Okra

LAND PREPARATION

For land preparation 2 ploughings were given with tractor driven cultivator and for levelling the field one-time laddering was also done. They applied 1trolley well rotten FYM per bigha during ploughing. On an average most of the households have cattle in their house and they stack cow dung in the manure heap.

Before final land preparation they apply 1trolley Cow-dung manure per Bigha land.

Rate of rent- ₹300/trolley. (Only transport cost)

Farmers who don't have manures they buy it at rent - ₹1200-1500/trolley

During final land preparation they use Tractor with rotavator to turn over the soil and mix with Cow-dung manures.

Some of the farmers still use indigenous implements like - country plough⁷ for land preparation. They do laddering after ploughing.

Rent:

Tractors with rotavator- ₹1000-1200 /hr.

Cultivator- ₹800-900/ hr.

After conversation with villagers, we got to know that -

5 farmers have their own tractors. We pen down the model's name and put down all the details from internet.

Tractor

Model -Mahindra Yuvo575 DI

- ❖ Engine HP – 41.1
- ❖ Wheel drive – 2WD
- ❖ Forward gears – 12
- ❖ Reverse gears – 3
- ❖ Brake Type – oil immersed
- ❖ Price – 6.5 lakh
- ❖ Age - 1-1.5 years
- ❖ No. of cylinder – 4
- ❖ Lifting Capacity - 1500 kg
- ❖ Clutch - Single / Dual
- ❖ Steering – Power steering

⁷ Some farmers rearing Bullocks and for preparation of nursery bed they used country plough, if someone rent bullocks they have to pay Rs. 300/- for half a day.

Rotavator

Model – SRT-5.5(170)/MS R+

- ✓ Overall length -1932 mm
- ✓ Overall width – 959 mm
- ✓ Overall height – 1116 mm
- ✓ Tilling width – 1795 mm
- ✓ Power- 50 - 65 HP
- ✓ 37 - 48 KW
- ✓ No. of tines – 60
- ✓ Transmission Type – Gear
- ✓ Max. working depth –203 mm
- ✓ Weight – 508 kg
- ✓ Age – 1 year
- ✓ Price – 80,000 – 90,000

Cultivator

Type	Rigid Cultivator
No Of Tynes	9 Tynes
Working Width	1860 mm
Brand	Mahindra
Suitable HP Range	35 hp & Above
Tractor Power	35-65 hp
Type of Mounting	3 Point Linkage
Overall Length	2000 mm
Overall Width	870 mm
Total Approx. Weight	265 kg
Shovel Points (Reversible)	63 mm
Loadability	65
Overall Height	1000 mm

Figure 13 Rotavator

Figure 12 Cultivator

Figure 11 Country Plough

Figure 15 Ploughing with country plough

Figure 14 Tractors

To know the nature of the soil of Bahadurpur, I randomly choose 5 fields in soil intervention week. I selected 5 random spots from every field and collected soil sample by cutting ‘V’ shaped cut. After collecting the soil, we test it in PSB soil testing laboratory and different value comes from different experiment. The results are as follows-

Soil sample	pH Value	EC Value(mS/cm)	Phosphorus value(abs)/R	Potassium value	Sulphur Value (abs)
C ₁	5.10	019	0.226	34.51	0.011
C ₂	5.12	0.09	0.196	12.09	0.061
C ₃	5.21	0.15	0.135	49.14	0.073

Soil sample	Fe value (mg/L)	Cu value (mg/L)	Zn value (mg/L)
C ₁	11.77	1.793	0.835
C ₂	30.16	2.151	1.083
C ₃	21.08	1.535	0.220

From the above result we can conclude that the nature of village Bahadurpur soil is **Moderately Acidic**⁸.

Average K present – 357 kg/ha, Average P content- 20 kg/ha, Average S content- 603 kg/ha
I suggested the farmers that they should apply lime for reclamation of the acidity.

I got to know that farmers have good awareness about applying organic matter to the soil. During ploughing the field to grow any crop, they apply well rotten cow dung, mustard oilcake. Also, some of the farmers grow Dhaincha as green manure crop 2months before sowing of rice.

I want to add that, proper training programme should be arranged by KVK to inform the farmers about different schemes and technologies for water resource management, soil conservation, and different benefits provided by the government. It would help them to grow crop in a sustainable way.

⁸ The farmers applied FMY not in sufficient quantity and applied gradually fertilizers in heavy quantity also canal water used as irrigation purpose that will inhibit acidity in their fields.

NURSERY BED MANAGEMENT AND TRANSPLANTING

Nursery seeding is done during May and June and transplanting is performed in July after onset of monsoon season. For 1 ha field, the seedbed size should be 1000m² of seedbed area (**1.5-2 katha/ Bigha**). FYM/compost is incorporated in the nursery. They separately don't treat the seeds with any chemical. For nursery bed preparation, 2 ploughing is given followed by one harrowing. After germination of seeds, 2.5 cm water depth is maintained.

- They use 30 days old seedlings for transplanting.
- They keep transplanting distance **20 x 15 or 15 x 15 cm** spacing.
- 2-3 seedlings/hill.

During RAWA Agronomy week I get to know about the above data from the farmers.

TRANSPLANTING- Transplanting is done generally 25-30 days after nursery bed preparation i.e., in the 1st week of August. For transplanting 4 labours are needed. (**Wages Rs. - 250/day/Labour**)

WATER MANAGEMENT - The main source of irrigation is canal and submersible. The cost for contractual submersible water is Rs. **2000/bigha/season**. They give irrigation based on the status of soil not depending on the critical stage of crops. Generally, 5cm water height is maintained in the rice field. They are using flooding system for giving the irrigation. Irrigation is withdrawn 15 days before harvesting.

The farmers are not using any type of special irrigation methods as they are not aware of these methods.

During Engineering and agronomy week and Extension week I get to know that Heavy Duty Petrol Pump, Honda water pump, Diesel Engine Water Pump etc were introduced in the year of 2000. Details of the machinery were collected from internet and farmers.

Figure 18 Submersible pump

Figure 16 Canal water

Figure 17 China Pump

Figure 20 irrigation applied

Figure 21 Tube well

Figure 19 Furrow irrigation

Honda Water Pump

- ✓ Model – WB 20 XD
- ✓ Power – 2.9 KW
- ✓ Age – 10 years
- ✓ Price- 16000
- ✓ Fuel tank capacity- 4L
- ✓ Discharge Capacity- 50,000 l/hr
- ✓ Delivery range- 900ft.
- ✓ Suction Pipe Length- 5m
- ✓ Fuel – petrol and kerosine used for running.

Heavy Duty Petrol Pump

- ✓ Model – 30P
- ✓ Power – 2 HP
- ✓ Age- 6 years
- ✓ Price – 10,000
- ✓ Discharge Capacity – 50 m (150ft.)
- ✓ Fuel tank capacity – 4L
- ✓ Fuel Consumption – 750ml/hr.
- ✓ Fuel – petrol and kerosine used for running.

Diesel Engine Water Pump

- ✓ Model – WPD 30
- ✓ Power – 5 HP, (331 CC)
- ✓ Age – 5 years
- ✓ Price- 12000
- ✓ Fuel tank capacity- 4.5 L
- ✓ Fuel Consumption - 1 l/hr (100m)
- ✓ Delivery Pipe Length – 300 ft. (100m)
- ✓ Suction Pipe Length- 5m (15 ft.)
- ✓ Fuel – Diesel

GENERAL WATER MANAGEMENT FOR ALL CULTIVATED CROPS

- Source of irrigation: Submersible pump, Canal, Sometimes Pond.
- Irrigation water (own/ rent): Rs.2000/Year/Bigha
- Irrigation scheduling (based on critical stage of the crop/ soil status): Water is given in land preparation time, after transplanting and in panicle initiation stage. Except all the farmers are generally supply water to the field when soil is getting dry and generally after 15-18 days.
- No. of irrigations: 5-6 (Depend on soil moisture availability)
- Methods of irrigation: Through submersible pump and canal water by using Honda pump⁹, diesel engine water pump.
- Drainage required, if any: If overflow of water is there then the small portion of soil from one side of the bund is cut and excess water is removed from the outlet channel.
- Soil moisture conservation practices followed or not: Not

NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT

During agronomy week we got to know farmers have used both the organic and chemical fertilizers for Kharif paddy cultivation. About **1-trolley FYM** is given per bigha land is provided. Regarding chemical fertilizers they mainly apply **10:26:26 NPK @20kg/bigha** as basal and urea **@10kg/bigha** is applied as top dressing. Some farmers also apply some micro nutrients. Rate of Urea **Rs. 8/kg, Rate of 10-26-26 Rs.25/kg.**

Brinjal: **10-26-26 @ 50-60kg /bigha**

Potato- **Mustard oil cake, DAP @ 1 bag / bigha, Cow dung @ 1 trolley**

⁹ In Bahadurpur village those farmers who don't have pump machine they can rented pump machine in lieu of either they give diesel oil + minimum rent of the machine or they give rent as per time required

GENERAL NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT OF ALL CULTIVATED CROPS

- Organic manure applied, if any: 1 Trolley of well rotten Cow dung manure is applied per Bigha and mix it with ploughing.
- Source of organic manure: Most of the farmers have cattle in their household from there they making FYM who haven't animals they collected from neighbour farmer.¹⁰
- Fertilizers applied & forms, methods of application: 10:26:26 as a source of NPK and Urea a source of nitrogen. Both the fertilizers are in granular form. Full 10:26:26 is given as basal and ½ urea given as basal and half as top dressing.
- Micronutrient applied & forms, methods of application: Anukhadya (Powder & granular form) Broadcasting.
- Nutrient deficiency symptoms, if any and correction: No
- Nutrient toxicity symptoms, if any and correction measures: No

WEED MANAGEMENT

In the paddy fields various types of weeds were observed mainly *Echinochloa crasgalli*, *Alternanthera philoxeroides*, *marsilea quadrifolia*, *Panicum repense*, *Cyperus iria*, *Echinochloa colona* etc. The farmers mainly used hand weeding method to control the weeds. Very few farmers use chemical (Glyphosate, Pendimethalin¹¹) for eradication of weeds. Two hand weeding are done. One hand weeding is given at 15-20 days after sowing and the other one is given at 40-45 days after sowing. They did not use any type of chemical herbicides as they think chemicals can harm their crops, besides that hand weeding process improves the crop growth. They faced 20 – 40% yield loss when failed to control weeds. They did not receive any type of awareness programs regarding the use of herbicides. 2 labours are needed for weeding per bigha (Wages Rs. - 250/day/Labour)

Major Weeds noticed in different crops

Brinjal – *Cynodon dactylon*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Panicum repense*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Amaranthus viridis*, *Tridax procumbens*, *Parthenium hysterophorousn* etc.

Potato- *Avena fatua*, *Chenopodium album*, *Cyperus iria*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Melilotus indica*, *Convolvulus arvensis* etc.

Chili- *Cynodon dactylon*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Convolvulus arvensis* etc.

Mustard- *Chenopodium album*, *Avena fatua*, *Cleome viscosa*, *Vicia sativa*, *Melilotus indica* etc.

Okra- *Elusine indica*, *cynodon dactylon*, *Cyperus rotundus* etc.

¹⁰ The farmers who don't have FYM in their home they can Purchased FYM @ 1500/trolley

¹¹ The farmers used Pendimethalin herbicide before or after 2-3 days sowing of transplanted rice

GENERAL WEED MANAGEMENT OF ALL CULTIVATED CROPS

- **Weed flora (names):** *Echinochloa crasgalli*, *Alternanthera philoxeroides*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Panicum repense*, *Cyperus iria*, *Echinochloa colona*, *Amaranthus viridis*, *Croton bonplandianum*, *Commelina benghalensis*, *Trianthema portulacastrum*, *Elusine indica*, *Paspalum distichum* etc.
- **Methods of weed control (mechanical/cultural/chemical/biological):** The farmers mainly used hand weeding method to control the weeds. Very few farmers use chemical (Glyphosate) for eradication of weeds.
- **Specify the method (hand weeding/ harrowing etc.):** Pulling out weeds by hand or uprooting weeds by using small hand tool is known as hand weeding¹². In this process the entire surface soil is dug to a shallow depth with the help of hand hoes, weeds are uprooted and removed.
- **What is the best way of controlling weeds?** They think hand weeding is the best method. Chemicals can harm their crops, besides that hand weeding process improves the crop growth.
- **Awareness and adoption level of weed management:** There is low awareness about the harmfulness of weeds among the farmers. So, they do not spend much time in weed eradication.
- **Practices (chemical/ mechanical/ cultural):** Most of the farmers use Mechanical or Physical method for weeding but some farmers use chemical method also.
- **Herbicide used (name and dose) in crops:** Hira-71 (Ammonium salt of glyphosate 71% SG, Systemic herbicide) Dose: 6-7gm/litre of Water or 1kg/Acre in 150-160 lit water. SAATHI (Pyrazosulfuron Ethyl 10% WP, Selective, Pre-emergence, early post-emergent, 60-80gms per acre or 150-200gms per hectare.)
- **Source of technical guidance for weed management:** Local herbicide shop owner or dealer.
- **Anticipated yield loss due to weeds in different crops if:** 15-20 %

Figure 25 *Croton bonplandianum*

Figure 22 *Amaranthus viridis*

Figure 24 *Marsilea quadrifolia*

Figure 23 *Cyperus iria*

¹² In hand weeding process the surface soil which are rich in organic matter are mixed with sub surface soil and incorporated the organic matter.

DISEASE AND PEST MANAGEMENT

Majra (Yellow Stem Borer) is the main pest for causing heavy yield loss. For controlling this pest most of the farmer used Ferterra (Chlorantraniliprole 0.4% w/w GR) @ 10 g/15 L of water. But according to the farmers this Ferterra is no longer effective against Majra insects. Some of the farmers also applied Virtako (Thimethoxam 1% + Chlorantraniliprole 0.5% GR) @ 1Kg/bigha. Some others applied Barroz (Cartap hydrochloride 7.5% w/w + Emamectin benzoate 0.25% w/w GR) @ 1.2 Kg/bigha for stem borer. We observed other pest of rice like-Gundhi Bug, Leaf folder, Yellow Stem borer, green leaf Hopper, Brown Plant Hopper. Different natural enemies also observed by us eg. Long jawed spider Dragon fly, Lady-bird beetle, Dragon fly, Damsel fly, Lady bird beetle. Different Pesticides applies in Bahadurpur village are - Starban, Contaf plus, Blightwar, Valxtra, Polytrin-C 44EC, Bavistin, Dhanulux, PROFEX Super, E-mate CALDAN 50 S.P.

Different disease observed in Rice field during our Plant Protection week- Brown spot, Blast, False smut, Grassy stunt, Sheath rot etc. According the farmer different chemicals they use for controlling disease are- 1. carmendazim 2. Hexaconazole 3. carbendazim 12%+ mancozeb 63% WP 4.Phosphamidon 40 SL 5. Chlorpyriphos 20 EC etc. During Plant Protection week we visited different input dealers shop and get to know about the chemicals applied in the field.

GENERAL DISEASE & PEST OBSERVED IN DIFFERENT CROPS OF VILLAGE

BAHADURPUR

Pest:

Brinjal – **Shoot & Fruit Borer** etc.
Potato-**PTM, Potato aphid** etc.
Mustard- **Mustard aphid, Pod borer** etc.

Disease:

Brinjal -**Little leaf of brinjal, Bacterial wilt.**
Potato- **Early blight, Late blight, Ring rot, Common Scab**
Mustard- **Alternaria Blight, Downey mildew.**
Cucumber- **Powdery mildew, scab, Fusarium wilt**

During Plant Protection Intervention weeks we noted down some information and calculated different parameters regarding pests e.g.-

- Variance - Mean ratio (VMR) = **1.65**
- Index of David and Moore (IDM) = **0.65**
- Index of Lexis = **1.28**
- Charlier Coefficient = **0.80**
- Simpson Index (D) = **0.13**
- Simpson index of diversity = **0.86**
- Simpsons reciprocal Index = **7.69**
- Pest: Defender (P:D) ratio = **1.57**

Figure 28 Gundhi Bug

Figure 29 GLH

Figure 26 Leaf Folder

Figure 31 Rice False Smut

Figure 30 Majra Poka (Yellow stem borer)

Figure 27 Insecticide

Figure 34 Leaf folder

Figure 33 BPH

Figure 32 Grass hopper

Figure 34 Leaf folder

Figure 33 BPH

Figure 32 Grass hopper

HARVESTING & THRESHING

The crop is generally harvested in the month of November. Harvesting¹³ is done when 80% panicles have ripened spikelets and their upper portion is become straw in brown or yellowish in colour. After harvested threshing is done by padded threshing machine. Rate of rent -Rs 150-200/ day. In the process of threshing two labourer is required @ Rs 250/day.

During agronomy week we came to know that most of the farmers harvest their crop manually with the help of sickle. Labour requirement **4-5 labourer/ Bigha** (Wage – Rs.250 /day)

For other crops like – Brinjal, Tomato, Chili, Pumpkin, Cucumber, Ridge gourd etc are harvested by hand picking.

For Potato, harvesting is done with the help of spade. For Mustard manual harvesting is done by sickle followed by winnowing.

¹³ After harvesting the Paddy, it is kept in field for 2-3 days for sun drying and then making truss.

YIELDS & MARKET PRICE

Average grain yield of rice is **5-6 q/bigha¹⁴**, **two kahon paddy straw** is produced from 1 bigha of paddy field. During village survey week we got to know that 20% of their produced grains they sale at local market @**Rs.1500-1600/Q** and remaining 80% they sales in Krishan Mandi @Rs. 1900-2000/Q. Straw is used for feeding live stocks and for making rope, thatching house etc, Remaining straw they sale @Rs.1500-2000/Kahon.

- Brinjal- 80-90 Q / acre @ Rs.20-25/kg
- Chili- 10-12 kg / katha @ Rs.50-60/kg
- Potato- 6 ton / Bigha @ Rs.10-20/kg
- Cucumber-7-8 q / 10 katha @ Rs.30-40/kg
- Rapeseed-Mustard-3-4q/Bigha @ Rs.40-45/kg

N.B.: Price of the produce vary according to season and market demand.

All the cultivated products are sold in the local market, Krishan mandi, Neighbour house.

STORAGE

After harvest, Farmer store the grains in the rural storage structure like – Morai. Straw is arranged and make a structure called Palui. Brinjal tomatoes, Okra, Chilli etc vegetable are freshly marketed in the local shop & Krishan mandi. Potato after sorting and grading they send it to the cold storage.

COST OF CULTIVATION OF 1 BIGHA PADDY

In village survey week we got to know from the farmers that how much cost is needed to cultivate 1 bigha Paddy. For land preparation and irrigation around Rs. 3000/bigha cost is needed. Cost of Pesticide application, Fertilizer & Seed is **Rs. 1810/Bigha**. During the whole cultivation 6-mandays of family labour and 10 hired labourer are required/bigha @ Rs.250/day/labourer. Cost of hired and own machinery – **Rs. 3100/bigha**. After calculating all kind of cost (Using cost concept) **Rs. 1565/q** expenditure is needed. Net return = **Rs. 3414**, Returns to management = **Rs. 2276** and returns per rupee = **1.29**. Annual Household Income of the family: **Rs. 74,950**. Annual Household Expenditure: **Rs. 50,520**. Annual savings: **Rs. 24,430**.

¹⁴ Yield is vary according to variety of seeds and input supplies(irrigation, fertilizers etc)

AVERAGE HOUSEHOLD DETAILS OF BAHADURPUR VILLAGE:

Bahadurpur villagers also do animal rearing as side income. Livestock present in Bahadurpur village are -Cow, Bullock, Goat, Sheep, duck, hen etc. On an average every household has 2-3 cows,4-5 goats, 2-3 ducks, 2-3 chickens. Total 3 pair of bullock present in Bahadurpur Village. 4-5 family rare 3-4 sheeps. Cow milk production- 3-4 lit/day, maximum proportion is used in home consumption and excess amount is sold at neighbour house and local market (rate -Rs. 30 /lit). Processed product they make – Ghee, Paneer, Curd, Kheer etc. 20-25 eggs produced /month and mostly consumed in home. Most of the raring breed is Desi. Animal raring house is made of - Kachha floor ground with corrugated Tin roof or Kachha floor ground with thatched floor or small brick and mud house. Average cost of dairy structure Rs. 10,000 to 15,000. Cattles are fed-Paddy straw, Grasses & Khol¹⁵, Grasses in the field and Chicken/Duck is fed- Paddy, Poultry Feed. Common disease observed in the livestocks- Foot and mouth disease, Black quarter (black-leg), Milk fever, Ranikhet disease etc. Treatment is done in Sriniketan Block Animal Health centre. Monthly health check-up cost- Rs. 10. One poultry farm was there in the village.

¹⁵ Mustard oil cake

In village Bahadurpur beside Paddy they also on an average every household has homestead garden and different kind of fruit, flowers and plantation crops are there. Some forestry plants are also there.

Fruit Plant Common Name	Botanical name	Number
Mango	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	145
Papaya	<i>Carica Papaya</i>	90
Guava	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	43
Lemon	<i>Citrus limon</i>	28
Coconut	<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	21
Jackfruit	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	34
Tamarind	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	9
Ber	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i>	22
Banana	<i>Musa sp.</i>	51
Drumstick	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	13

Table: showing the information about fruit plants

From the above table it can be cleared that mostly mango, papaya, banana, Guava are the dominating fruit pants which are seen in most of the homestead garden of the village Bahadurpur. Most of them are in vegetative and fruiting stage and in good condition

Agro-Forestry Plants Common Name	Botanical Name	Number
Neem	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	42
Kolke Ful Or Holud Karabi	<i>Thevetia peruviana</i>	21
Rosewood or Shisham	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i>	15
Bamboo	<i>Bambusa tulda</i>	75
Sonajhuri	<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i>	11
Mehogeny	<i>Swietenia mahogoni</i>	5
Sandal wood	<i>Santalum album</i>	2
Basil or Tulsi	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i>	170

Table: showing the different Agro-forestry plants in homestead

Information about the annuals and biennials (Vegetables/Spices/Flowers) found in the respondents homestead garden

Common name	Botanical name	Season of Growing
Sponge Gourd	<i>Luffa cylindrica</i>	Winter
Brinjal	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Winter
Chilli	<i>Capsicum annum</i>	Winter and rainy
Malabar Spinach	<i>Basella alba</i>	Summer
Spinach	<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>	Winter
Radish	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	Winter
Punka Shak	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	Winter
Marigold	<i>Tagetes Sp</i>	Winter
Four-o'clock Flower	<i>Mirabilis jalapa</i>	Winter
Periwinkle	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	All season
Holy Basil	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	All season
Asian pigeonwings (Aparajita)	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>	All season
Rangana Flower	<i>Ixora coccinea</i>	All season
Jaba	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	All season
Rose	<i>Rosa indica</i>	Winter
Karabi	<i>Nerium Oleander</i>	All season
Kochu	<i>Colocasia esculenta</i>	All season
Rheo Plant	<i>Rhoeo Discolor</i>	All season

Their homestead garden is mainly consisting of different annual and biennials like vegetables and flower crops. Most of the household cover the vegetables, and flowers. Spices are negligible in number. They carefully cultivate the crops for their household consumption. They mostly cultivate holy basil, chilli, Punka shak, Spinach, brinjal in different season.

Vegetables and fruit produced are mostly used for home consumption and excess amount is sold at Local market.

Major plantation crops present in the village is coconut. Major spices plant present in the village- Turmeric, Coriander etc.

Post-harvest handling or processing of horticultural products are not done in large scale. But for home consumption – Mango pickle¹⁶, Amchur¹⁷, Coconut ball (Naru) etc. are prepared.

Figure 37 Aamchur

Figure 36 Coconut jaggery ball

Figure 35 Mango pickle

¹⁶ In pickle or other processed products the villages not added any kind of preservatives only natural preservatives are used, it can used up to 6-8 months.

¹⁷ Dried sliced mango

POULTRY FARM

Owner name – Biswanath Ghosh. Structure: Corrugated tin sheet with Bamboo and cemented pillar (no. of 9) structure along with water feeding system. 4 side walls are covered with net. Length of poultry farm structure is 100 ft, width is 20 ft and height is 15 ft. Length of side wall is 7 ft. Total 40 feeder were there in the farm. Total 35 drinker were there in the farm. Litter: Earthen floor with rice chaff and straw-mulch. Capacity: 1500-piece (summer) 1600 piece (Winter). Purpose: Only meat purpose. Breed (IB- Indian Broiler): i) Ross breed (2kg wt. within 35 days) ii) Crop Breed. Worker: Along with owner 1 worker works there. Wage: Rs.300/Day.

DIFFERENT AGRO-BASED INDUSTRY PRESENT IN VILLAGE- BAHADURPUR

PUFFED RICE PROCESSING

Visited place: Annapurna Muri Mill, Bahadurpur, Birbhum, Owner: Abanidhar Ghosh, Age of Mill: 8 Years

Cost: 8-10 Lakh (All house + Machinery), Daily Labours: 3 (Wages: ₹250/day), Packeting Labours: 4 (1 quintal packeting charges ₹100.)

Processing: 10kg rice + 2kg salt + required amount of cold water. Rice grains are withdrawn from the chamber after fully soaked and salt were fully dissolved. Then sun drying (1-2 days of good sunlight) is done. After that dried grains are poured in puffed rice processing machine. (Rate = 150-200 kg/hour.) To run the machine diesel is used. Puffed rice are collected in the small buckets and transferred into another house. Packeting was done there. 500gm, 250gm, and 200 gm packets are made. Price of the packets -500 gm packet (₹20), 250 gm packet (₹10), 200 gm packet (₹8).

MUSTARD OIL EXTRACTION

Shop Name: Garai Atta chaki, Binuria. Owner: Monoranjan Garai. Age of mill: 25 years.

Processing: Expeller press is a screw type machine that mainly Presses oil suck thorough a caged burned like cavity. One side of the place takes the raw material and other side give the other products. The uses friction and continuous pressure from the screw drive to move and compresses threshed material. The oil is extracted from the seeds through small openings and rest materials are removed from the machine as cake. Cost of machine (₹1.5 lakh when purchased from 1 kg white or yellow mustard - max. 450-500 gm oil is extracted from black mustard 250- 300 hm oil cake can be extracted charging ₹6/kg.

WHEAT FLOUR MILLING INDUSTRY

Shop Name: Garai Atta chaki, Binuria. Owner: Monoranjan Garai. Age of mill: 25 years.

Cost of establishment: 4.5 lakhs. Efficiency: 30-40 kg/hour. Cost of milling: Rs. 5/kg. Packets available: 1kg(32rupees) and 500 gm. Processing: Cleaning: sticks, stones and other such impurities are removed from the wheat. Tempering and conditioning: At this stage, the

wheat is soaked in water to easily remove the bran. Conditioning is done before milling to ensure moisture content is uniform throughout the grain.

Gristing: This is a particularly important stage where, the conditioned wheat and cleaned wheat are mixed to create the required type and quality of flour. **Separating:** The grist then goes through a series of rolls which rotate at various speed levels. The rolls only split the wheat grain open to separate the inner white portion from the bran. **Milling:** The wheat is grounded by a machine that crushes it into pieces. It is then put through sifters from which the meal obtained is processed further with repeated grinding and sifting. Then, the meal becomes fine flour, wheat germ and wheat bran. **Blending:** Here, constituents are mixed to produce different flours. For instance, a blend of wheat bran and white flour, produce whole wheat flour.

SWEET PROCESSING INDUSTRY

Shop Name: Ghosh Mishtanno vandar. Owner: Sushanta Ghosh. Labours: 2 (Daily wages 250-300 rupees) Utensils are used: Iron and stainless-steel. Processing – Take curd "Channa" (Indian Cottage Cheese) (5kg). Then separate the Channa and Whey by draining in a muslin cloth. Then remove the excess whey by pressing it with some heavy metal or stone. Then add 100gm sugar+ flour+ arrow root in winter+ cardamom with Channa and mix it very well. Then solid mixture of ingredients are cut into small pieces and make it round like balls (80 pieces for 5 rupees each and 60 pieces for 6-7 rupees each) After that cook the balls in concentrated sugar syrup till they turn light and spongy. When it becomes fluffy or Spongy, remove it from the concentrated sugar Syrup and dip into diluted Syrup or milk.

DIFFERENT INSTITUTION PRESENT IN VILLAGE BAHADURPUR

EDUCATIONAL

1. Bahadurpur Primary School, there was only one school which was very far from Bahadurpur village, due to far distance it was very difficult to attend school in rainy and winter days, also the road was Kacha Road, everywhere hole and mud in the road in rainy season. So looked into these circumstances the local influencer decided to established a school here in Bahadurpur. They gave land for school building and grant funds from their own collection. Later the school was registered in Primary Education Board, from now onward the school maintained by government of West Bengal itself. The school renewed in 2001 and developed in every sphere of education for all. Year of Establishment: 1944, Name of the Office Bearer: President: Tuli Mazumdar, there are 3 teachers present in the school. Total strength of the school- 46. Organizational Set-up: Office Room (1), Class Room (3), Kitchen (1), Latrine (1), Bathroom (1)Submersible pump (1). In kitchen 3 workers are there in the school (wage-Rs.1500).

2. MANAB JAMIN SISHU KENDRA (BAHADURPUR): It is a non-Govt. Organisation (NGO). Head: Anuradha Chatterjee (owner) provides Money and Infrastructure for this institution. 2 teachers teaches in this organisation. Total number of members – 30. Membership Fees – Rs. 20/- per month. Type of Activities of the organization -Pre-primary study, Games & Sports, Drawing and Writing Competition, Singing and Dancing Competition.

3. Bahadurpur Anganwadi Centre, one centre is there. Different educational activities and health facilities are provided here for 0–4-year child and pregnant women. They also provide nutritious food for them and provides sanitary facility to women and health support. They also provide learning material (ABACUS, BOOKS, Puzzle etc.)

RELIGIOUS

In Bahadurpur village most of are hindu. So some hindu temples are there like Bahadurpur Sarbojonin Durga Mandir (2 in numbers), Dharmarajtala , Manasha Temple , Kali temple(5) and one Shiva temple. For the maintenance of these temples, funds are collected from every household of villages during festival.

There is also a club in village Bahadurpur and a library is there near the Anganwadi. Library is opened in every saturday after 2 weeks.

POLITICAL

In Bahadurpur village people are united under the leader's decision. The villagers participated in leaders call on the matters of different village activity, family matters, judgement on any issues and decision will be taken on beneficial environment of the village

and welfare of the people. There is a village level **Supervisor and a Convenor** who are inspect all ongoing panchayat works.

The Supervisor and Convenor are answerable to the **Member** of the Panchayat, and member is answerable to the **Pradhan**¹⁸ of the Panchayat. Pradhan is a head in Local Self Government, who execute all works at village level and welfare of the villages.

After the Pradhan next is **Block Development Officer (BDO)**¹⁹ and then **District Magistrate (DM)**²⁰ is the Local Self Government responsible for village welfare.

They sometimes visit to block office ADO office, RKVK and oftenly visit to bank. They get agricultural info. from Block Office, ADA Office., KPS, KVK / Ag. College, Neighbours, Dealers, Newspaper, Radio, Television. They mostly rely on dealers, neighbours, television, ADO office etc.

MOBILITY MAPPING ²¹OF VILLAGERS (VENN DIAGRAM)

¹⁸ Rupur Gram Panchayat, Rupur, West Bengal

¹⁹ Sriniketan Block Office, Sriniketan, West Bengal

²⁰ District Magistrate Office in Suri, West Bengal

²¹ Mobility mapping represents villagers used to access these places according to the distance and size of the institution.

CONSTRAINTS OF VILLAGE BAHADURPUR

1. Crop depends on monsoon.
2. Poor nutritional status of soil.
3. Small fragmented plot size.
4. Undulated topography creates problems.
5. Poor irrigation facility.
6. Required inputs are not Available.
7. Crop doesn't get a response to technologies.
8. Loss due to pest attack.
9. Insufficient technical help.
10. Low investment capacity.
11. Poor benefit-cost ratio.
12. Poor knowledge about improved technologies.
13. Transportation.
14. Storage.

SWOT ANALYSIS OF BAHADURPUR VILLAGE

Enumerate the SWOT of the village with respect to farming and prepare a developmental plan considering constraints and SWOT.

STRENGTH

RANK

1. Owned farmland
2. Indigenous Knowledge
3. Canal nearby
4. Local village level institution
5. Resource availability

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

WEAKNESS

RANK

1. Unity is less
2. New technology adaptation
3. Lack of money
4. Local storage problem
5. Lack of export facilities

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

OPPORTUNITY

RANK

1. Emerging tradition of collective action through the agricultural extension system
2. Good understanding marketing
3. Arising awareness of villagers and education
4. Existence of agricultural insurance

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

THREAT

RANK

1. Disease and pests that are resistance to pesticide
2. Unwanted environmental disaster
3. low price and increase in production cost
4. youth are not interested in farming

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Developmental plan to overcome Weakness and Threats

1. Organize frequent meetings and discussion among farmers
2. On Farm Trail should be done.
3. Providing agricultural loan
4. Making general storing hub
5. Government initiative is needed for exporting
6. Use right quantity pesticide and also use natural pesticide
7. Depends on Agro-meteorological department for weather related news
8. farmers should adopt in diversity in cropping system
9. The youth should understand the need of agriculture and the importance in future days.

We performed Method demonstration on Azolla cultivation in extension week in Bahadurpur village.

METHOD DEMONSTRATION OF AZOLLA CULTIVATION

Date- 20/11/22

Time- 10 AM

Place- Bahadurpur Sarbojanin Durga Mandir Prangyan.

Topic- Azolla cultivation.

Objective - To Enrich the knowledge of the farmer about Azolla cultivation and to encourage farmer to grow Azolla.

LOCATION OF DEMONSTRATION

In Bahadurpur village as we discussed with the villagers for best place of our demonstration, they suggest us to 'Dharam er Aathchala' is the best place because it was beside the road and providing us electricity also. So, we agreed to their suggestion and we perform our demonstration in that place.

DATE OF DEMONSTRATION

We selected 20th November, 2022 as our final demonstration day, so all the arrangements were held according kept in mind that day.

LEAFLETS, BANNER PRINTING & POSTER DESIGN:

We think it was mandatory for our demonstration to print a banner and leaflets and making some poster for short message highlighted on it.

DECORATORS AND PROJECTOR ARRANGEMENTS

On the day of the programme we reached the venue at 9 am and did the all necessary set up

1. Hanging of banner and poster
2. Set up projector
3. Chair table arrangements.
4. Packeting azolla
5. All the necessary equipment need to demonstrate are arranged.

AZOLLA COLLECTION

We collected azolla from our Rathindra Krishi Vigyan Kendra, we convinced Dr. Subrata Mondal for knowledge about azolla multiplication and showed them how its multiplied

LEAFLETS PASTING

2 days before the programme we invited all the villagers with leaflets. Some leaflets we stuck on the walls.

ON THE DAY OF DEMONSTRATION

At 10.30 the villagers came on the spot along with our teachers **Dr. Kishore Chandra Swain** and **Dr. Darshan N.P.**

At first our Group member **Akash Mondal** started the programme with his brief speech on "What Is Azolla?" And He showed some pictures of azolla on the Screen accordingly.

Next, my friend, **Sonali Shil** described about the Benefit of Azolla as N₂ fertilizer replacement and as animal feed and showed some pictures of azolla growing on paddy field. then Our friend **Nisha Ghosh** Explained the villagers about How to feed and how much azolla should be given/day to an animal with sowing related pictures on the screen.

Then I, **Pathik Sutradhar** described the process and preparation of growing azolla elaborately and some of our friends (**Nayan Ghosh, Prothoma Sarkar, Nishat Tasnim, Dechen Sherpa, Prabhati Hansda, prosonno Biswas**) trained the villagers manually sowing the whole process step by step on the spot.

Then our member **Mukesh Mahato** Told the farmer about The Different Difficulties and disease occur during cultivation of azolla and our friend **Raju Halder** told them how to overcome the difficulties and how to cure the disease of Azolla.

My friend **Rahul Dey** said the Farmers the cost of Azolla cultivation and from where to collect Azolla and some success story of Farmers with photo documentary.

Then we concluded our presentation part with a slogan:

"ঘরে ঘরে অ্যাজোলা চাষ লাগবে কাজে বারোমাস"

DOUBT CLEARING SESSION

After that we did a Question answer session and some curious farmer asked us their doubts and questions and we gave them proper answer.

ARRANGEMENTS OF TIFFIN

Tiffin packets and some sweets were distributed among the invited Villagers.

AZOLLA SAMPLE DISTRIBUTION

We distributed some azolla sample among interested farmers.

Some farmers came to us and said that they are very much interested and willing to cultivate azolla in their house and in paddy field.

CONCLUSION

It is the most suitable method for teaching farmers of all age groups, especially in village level. This might help in removing objections regarding the non-availability of the learning by doing approach

INTERACTING WITH FARMERS

KVK/RESEARCH STATION ATTACHMENT

GENERAL INFORMATION OF RATHINDRA KRISHI VIGYAN KENDRA (RKVK)

Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) established the Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK) mandated for the District of Birbhum, West Bengal on the 4th October, 1994 under the administrative control of Palli Siksha Bhavana (Institute of Agriculture), Visva-Bharati, Sriniketan, Birbhum, West Bengal. This Krishi Vigyan Kendra was named as Rathindra Krishi Vigyan Kendra to pay tributes homage and regards to Sri Rathindranath Tagore, the eldest son of gurudev Rabindranath Tagore and the "Un-sung Hero of Indian Agriculture", the man who was the guiding force behind the whole "Sriniketan Experiment", one of the few living Agricultural Extension Efforts, launched in the pre-independent India. The "Sriniketan Experiment" model was basically aimed at Rural reconstruction and this KVK was made for the farming community and Agricultural practitioners of Birbhum district.

MANDATE OF KRISHI VIGYAN KENDRA

Previously, the mandate of KVK was: "Assessment, refinement and dissemination of technologies and products coming out from the National Agricultural Research System (NARS)". (Technologies-e.g., System of Rice Intensification, Zero Tillage etc; products-e.g., cono weeder, seed drill etc.) One needs to keep in mind the fact that dissemination of technology and products is fully looked up by the State Department of Agriculture, since as per the constitution, agriculture is a state subject.

The modified and presently accepted mandate of the KVKs is: Assessment and Dissemination of technologies and products coming out from the National Agricultural Research System (NARS). The Krishi Vigyan Kendras provide intensive hands on training in various aspects of agriculture, horticulture, animal husbandry and so on to encourage unemployed farm youth and farmwomen to start their own agro based enterprise in their locality. These KVKs would also conduct on-farm testing (OFT) of various agricultural and allied technologies for refinement and conduct frontline demonstrations (FLD) on oilseeds, cereals and pulses etc.

ACTIVITIES OF RKVK

For the realization of the mandate effectively, the following activities are envisaged for Rathindra KVK: -

1. On-farm testing to assess the location specificity of agricultural technologies under various farming systems.
2. Frontline demonstrations to establish production potential of technologies on the farmers' fields.

3. Capacity development of farmers and extension personnel to update their knowledge and skills on modern agricultural technologies.
4. To work as Knowledge and Resource Centre of agricultural technologies for supporting initiatives of public, private and voluntary sector in improving the agricultural economy of the district.
5. Providing farm advisories using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and other media means on varied subjects of interest to farmers.
6. Long duration skill and entrepreneurship development training programmes for rural youth.

In addition, Rathindra KVK produces quality technological products (seed, planting material, bio-agents, livestock etc.) and makes it available to farmers, organize frontline extension activities, identify and document selected farm innovations and converge with ongoing schemes and programs within the mandate of Rathindra KVK.

ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURE

Rathindra Krishi Vigyan Kendra has the following 6 departments/specializations:

1. Agronomy
2. Fisheries
3. Animal Science
4. Crop Protection
5. Home Science
6. Agricultural Extension

These subjects are exclusive to RKVK and are bound to vary in other KVKs, depending upon the most popular agricultural enterprises in those areas.

TECHNICAL ACHIEVEMENTS

The activities of Rathindra Krishi Vigyan Kendra are focused on the following priority Thrust Areas: -

1. Crop diversification through introduction of Pulses, Oilseeds, major Millets, horticultural crops like Elephant Foot Yam, Drum Stick and high value low volume horticultural products like Capsicum, Broccoli etc.
2. Popularization of High Yielding Varieties (HYVs) of major crops like Rice, Wheat, Mustard, Potato etc. as well as traditional varieties of those crop also.
3. Cultivation of field crops which require least water in the Arid and Semi-Arid regions of the district and cultivation of suitable horticultural crops in those regions.
4. Popularization of improved management practices of Animals and fishes.
5. Women empowerment through Rural Crafts and Nutritional Management of Rural Women and Children
6. Market led Extension, Crop Insurance and institutional Rural Credit flow Mechanism.

LIST OF FAMILY MEMBERS IN RATHINDRA KRISHI VIGYAN KENDRA

SI No	Designation	Name of the Incumbent
1	Senior Scientist & Head	Dr. Subrata Mandal
2	Subject Matter Specialist	Sri Sourav Mondal
3	Subject Matter Specialist	Dr. Prabuddha Ray
4	Subject Matter Specialist	Dr. Madhuchhanda Khan
5	Programme Assistant (Computer Programmer)	Sri Suraj Kumar Bhakta
6	Programme Assistant (Farm Manager)	Sri Palash Ankure
7	Driver-cum-Mechanic	Sri Krishna Bansi Chatterjee
8	Driver-cum-Mechanic	Sri Bikash Chandra Ghosh
9	Supporting staff	Sri Chowdhury Md. Anwar
10	Supporting staff	Sri NaranTudu

ON FARM TRIALS CONDUCTED AT RKVK

On farm trials are research trials with the objective to predict how different management options will perform compared to each other under a particular environment and cropping system. OFTs are different from other types of trials because of the fact that they involve the active participation of the farmers. Whereas all other trials are conducted at SAUs or Research stations and is guided by a supervisor, the OFTs are conducted in the farmer's field with both the scientist and the farmer acting as the supervisor. OFTs are designed based on the particular problems of the locality. OFTs are both scientifically and statistically important. In an OFT, it is essential to take the farmer's feedback to look for additional problems that arise and derive further scope of research. If the results of an OFT are consistent for 2 consecutive years, then it is advanced to Front Line Demonstration. If the results are not consistent for 2 years, then the OFT is repeated for another year. In all, it can be stated that OFT is "problem-solving research" and "farmer's field-based research".

FRONT LINE DEMONSTRATIONS CONDUCTED AT RKVK

FLDs are scientifically and statistically designed demonstrations with the objective of demonstrating the potential of newly released technologies in farmers' condition. The special features of FLDs are:

- ❖ FLDs are conducted under the close supervision of the scientists of NARS comprising ICAR Institutes, NRCs, Project Directorates, KVKs, SAUs and RRSs.
- ❖ Only newly released technologies or those likely to be released in the near future are selected for FLDs.
- ❖ FLDs are organized in blocks of 5 ha involving all those farmers whose plots fall in the identified demonstration block (Cluster FLD approach).
- ❖ Only critical inputs and training are provided from the scheme budget, remaining inputs are supplied by the farmers themselves.

- ❖ Training of the farmers associated with the FLDs is a pre-requisite for the program.

The purpose is to convince extension functionaries and farmers together about the potentialities of technologies for further wide scale diffusion.

IMPORTANT NATIONAL PROGRAMMES IMPLEMENTED BY RKVK:

1. Soil Health Card
2. Doubling Farmers' Income by 2022
3. Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY)
4. Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana (PMKSY) (More crop per drop)
5. Kisan Credit Card (KCC).
6. Swacchata activities (segregation of biodegradable and non-biodegradable wastes, emphasis on Vermicomposting and NADEP composting)
7. CFLD on pulses and oilseeds.

SCHEMATIC VIEW OF RKVK

OUR ACTIVITIES IN KVK

We are involved in various practical works in the RKVK

Preparation of Azolla (Date 20th Oct 2022)

Definition

Azolla is a unique freshwater fern that is one of the fastest growing plants on the planet due to its symbiotic relationship with a cyanobacterium ('blue-green alga') called anabaena. Anabaena draws down the atmospheric nitrogen that fertilizes azolla, and azolla provides a nitrogen-filled home for anabaena within its leaf cavities. This enables the plant to double its biomass in as little as two days free floating on water as shallow as one inch (2.4 cm).

Preparation

1. At first small vessel were taken individually by each of us.
2. Then we filled water in the vessel leaving the top 15-20 cm.
3. After that we had taken 2 full hand of 3-4 days old cow dung and mixed it finely with water in a bucket.
4. Then we took 2 mugs of the cow dung liquid mixture and added it into each water filled vessels and mixed it properly in circular way by our hand.
5. Then we left the mixture for 10-15 minutes.
6. Next, we added 2 tea-spoon of SSP (Single Super Phosphate) in the vessel and mixed it by hand.
7. After that we left the mixture 10-15 minutes.
8. Finally, we took 1 full hand of fresh azolla and spread it on our vessel.

We Checked the growth of Azolla regularly 7 days interval. The growth was massive.

Swacchata Activities & Preparation of Vermicompost (Date 21th Oct 2022)

Definition

Vermicompost (vermi-compost) is the product of the decomposition process using various species of worms, usually red wigglers, white worms, and other earthworms, to create a mixture of decomposing vegetable or food waste, bedding materials, and vermicast. This process is called vermicomposting.

Preparation

1. At first, we dug 4 hole and 4 peg were stuck into it.
2. Then the Polythene portable vermicompost bed were placed perfectly.
3. Then we collected weeds from Finger millet field and nearby area of KVK.
4. Weeds were cut into small pieces by Boti for well decomposition.
5. Then we took some cow-dung and mixed it in a bucket with water. Cow dung speeds up the decomposition process.
6. Then we filled a layer with weed and spread cow-dung water on the top, and this process continued until the bed is filled leaving upper 30 cm.

We visited the vermicompost bed 3-4 days interval and spread water into it for decomposition. After 15 days or after partial decomposition earth worm need to be spread on it and after 45 days sundried vermicompost are packed.

Determination of Harvest Index of Finger millet at RKVK (Date 24-25th Nov 2022)

Definition

Harvest index (HI) is the ratio of grain to total shoot dry matter and is as a measure of reproductive efficiency.

HI was calculated according to the following formula: Harvest index (%) = (Grain yield / Biological yield) × 100.

Procedure

1. At first, we made a group of some students.
 2. then we started harvesting the ragi by sickle and tied up and made heaps.
- Note:** the panicle of ragi seeds (Economic yield) were already harvested by KVK staffs
3. Then we took the weight of our harvested ragi (only biological yield) and noted the value and gave it to Subrata sir.

Our group had harvested ragi up to 2 days.

1st day - 40kg, 18 kg

2nd day - 32 kg.

Calculation of Harvest Index

Total grain yield harvested by KVK staffs = 100

Total biological yield harvested by all our group = 523.12

Then Harvest Index (%) = $(100 / 523.12) \times 100 = 19.11$

Removal of termitarium from Mango Orchard (Date 29th Nov 2022)

Objective

Removal of termite and mound from the mango orchard.

Method

1. At first, we made a pair of 2 students and selected some termite affected plants in the orchard.
2. Then we took a wooden stick and rubbed on the termite mound.
3. Then water was spread on the affected trees and cleaned it properly.
4. Then some chemicals were sprayed later by KVK staffs to control the termite attack.

Land preparation and sowing of chickpea (Date 30th Nov– 2nd Dec 2022)

Procedure

1. After harvesting of Finger millet, we watered the whole plot and left it for 1 day.
2. On next day we ran the power tiller all over the field.
3. When the soil loosened up, we picked up and threw all the ragi stubbles and weeds by our hand and with the help of rake.
4. Then we calculated fertilizer dose for 450 sq. meter area of our field and the required amount of fertilizer (2 kg Urea, 11.5 kg SSP, 1.5 kg MOP) were broadcasted.
5. Again, the power tiller was run again all over the field for mixing the fertilizer with soil, and leftover stubbles and weeds were Removed by hand.
6. Then we divided our field into 4 plots.
7. We made rows of 30 cm spacing with the help of line drawing Desi plough or Hand drawn tines.
8. Chickpea seeds (GNG2299) were taken and sown at 10 cm spacing.

World soil Day celebration at RKVK (Date 5th Dec 2022)

Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) through its research institutions and KVKs celebrated this year World Soil Day 2022 under the theme “Soils: Where food begins” on 5th December 2022 throughout the country. An international day to celebrate soil was recommended by the International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS) in 2002.

In Rathindra Krishi Vigyan Kendra world soil day were celebrated on this 5th December as a means to focus attention on the importance of healthy soil and to advocate for the sustainable management of soil resources.

1. We arrived RKVK at 9 am.
2. All the Farmers were present there with us
3. Dr. Arun Kumar Barik, Dr. Jayanta Kumar Chatterjee, Dr. Goutam Kumar Ghosh of Palli Shikkha bhavana institute of Agriculture were there as guest lecturer.
4. Dr. Subrata Sarkar Started the programme with his speech.
5. Then Dr. Jayanta Kumar Chatterjee, Dr. Goutam Kumar Ghosh and Dr. Ak Barik delivered their speech on the importance of Soil and soil health.
6. Then soil health card were distributed among the Farmers.
7. And we the students described the process of reading Soil health card and told them about the value indicating which type of soil they have and which type of nutrients are deficient, what they have to apply to reclaim their field etc.
8. Then we had our lunch at RKVK along with our Farmers.

Weeding at RKVK Lawn (Date 6th Dec 2022):

We were instructed to clear the weeds of lawn of the RKVK.

1. At first, we loosened the soil with Khurpi.
2. Then we removed the weeds by our hands.

MY EXPERIENCE IN KVK

From this KVK attachment programme we are able to the various activities of Rathindra Krishi Vigyan Kendra. We have learned about the history, genesis, activities, impact and various success stories of RKVK. During the whole course of RAW (Rural Agricultural Work Experience) I gained a lot of knowledge. As it is a fieldwork and I got the opportunity to interact with my farmer, I came to know the practical difficulties one use to face in cultivation. Theoretical knowledge is now combined with true practical knowledge. I am again thankful to the course instructor for kind help and guidance through the whole RAW course. Lack of awareness, many problem etc. were the constraints to undertake the new technology of cultivation and other. I am very much sure about my experience on KVK will definitely helped me in future.

SUGGESTION

- Market access of the village should be improved.
- Major disease and pest should be treated with proper chemicals.
- They should come out from conventional paddy practices and should move into vegetables and fruit Practices.
- Farmers of Bahadurpur village has very small land holding so they still use sickle to harvest paddy and it consumes much times and money so if the farmers come together and use combine harvester then it will be more fruitful and time-saving.
- Processing is not so good in the village. If they start processing of different products then the spoilage of the raw fruits and vegetables will be less.
- Improve Storage facilities are not there in the village. If proper storage is constructed, it will definitely help farmers.
- Bahadurpur village farmers are poor and don't have that much idea about water resource and soil conservation techniques. If government and KVK make them learn that how to manage soil and water, the farmers will be benefited and in near future the soil erosion and water scarcity can be checked.

CONCLUSION

By doing the survey in Bahadurpur village, I can conclude that, the villagers are mainly grow paddy. In case of fruit crops or vegetables, they only cultivate in their home gardens. A few farmers cultivate vegetables in the fields. The main reason for this is the lack of awareness of vegetable cultivation and the less availability of marketing facilities of vegetables and fruits. The RAW course has given us really good opportunities to get attached with the farmers and with their package of practices which help us to gather practical knowledge and experiences regarding crop production. During the survey, I have observed that most of the farmers are facing problems of aberrant weather conditions and increasing disease-pest infestations. Due to these, all the farmers growing paddy, potato, mustard are suffering a lot. Some farmers are spraying pesticides but not getting results to their satisfaction. So, it requires rethinking and needs proper solution to combat these problems. Another thing is, most of the farmers are much dependent on labour force for the farming operations. This is increasing the cost of cultivation and the profit margin is decreasing gradually. So, at this moment farmers

should think more about farm mechanization. They need more training and education for better sustainable farming practices and only by this the overall development of agriculture and the village can be achieved. After doing this survey we got a clear-cut knowledge about major insect pest attacks and their damage symptoms in the real field condition. After talking to different farmers, we got to know that they are mostly rely on Chemicals and insecticide and they don't have proper knowledge about Natural enemy and ETL (Economic threshold level). During this Village Survey week, we get to know about the cropping pattern and farming system, cost of cultivation of paddy / bigha of village Bahadurpur. We get to know about the annual expenditure and income of households and from this information we can say that the socio-economic status of the villagers and most of them are comes under middle class family. As it is a fieldwork and I got the opportunity to interact with my farmer, I came to know the practical difficulties one use to face in cultivation. Theoretical knowledge is now combined with true practical knowledge. I am again thankful to the course instructor for kind help and guidance through the whole course. Soil and water are 2 important growth factors in the agriculture sector. The poor farmers of Bahadurpur village do not have adequate resources to implement erosion control practices and mitigate the threat of soil erosion in this village which require greater needs. The main causes of enhanced soil erosion are intensive cultivation, urbanization, overgrazing, poor management of arable soils and deforestation. Soil deserves more attention as it is being eroded faster than its formation. Agricultural productivity and environmental quality is sustained by managing and alleviating the off-site and on-site impacts of accelerated soil erosion here in the village.

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